

Greenhouse evaluation of granular, wettable powder, and flowable insecticide formulations for tungro prevention

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Some insecticides appear to prevent tungro infection in addition to killing the green leafhopper vector *Nephotettix virescens*. Greenhouse trials evaluated three insecticide formulations (see table). Three replications of 20 35-day-old Taichung Native 1 plants planted in 50- × 50- × 10-cm galvanized trays were tested. Granular insecticides (2 kg ai/ ha) were broadcast on the soil surface. Wettable powder and flowable insecticides (0.1% concentration) were sprayed on plants. At 1 and 5 days after treatment

(DAT) each plant was inoculated with 2 viruliferous *N. virescens*. An equal number of untreated plants were inoculated as a check. Insect mortality was recorded 48 hours after caging, and infected plants were counted 20 days after inoculation. Virus infection prevention was calculated:

$$\% \text{ prevention} = \frac{\% \text{ infected plants in control} - \% \text{ infected plants in treatment}}{\% \text{ infected plants in control}} \times 100$$

Of granular insecticides tested, carbofuran prevented virus infection at 1 DAT. At 5 DAT it was 89% successful. MIPC, bendiocarb, and BPMC also effectively prevented the virus. All 4 insecticides caused 100% vector mortality.

Although disulfoton, mephosfolan, and phorate also gave 100% vector mortality, they did not prevent tungro virus infection. The remaining granular insecticides

were ineffective in either preventing virus infection or killing the vector.

Acephate (wetable powder [WP]) and carbofuran (foliar) prevented tungro infection 100% at 1 DAT. At 5 DAT, they prevented it 89%. Bendiocarb (WP), carbaryl (WP), and MIPC (WP) also effectively prevented the virus infection.

These 5 insecticides caused 100% vector mortality. DDT (WP) and BHC (WP) neither killed the vector nor prevented virus infection.

Results indicate that insecticides that control the vector do not necessarily prevent virus infection. The reasons are obscure, suggesting that insecticides that prevented infection should be tested in the field. ✎

Effect of granular, wettable powder, and flowable insecticides on rice tungro virus infection and *N. virescens* mortality,^a Cuttack, India.

Insecticide		Prevention of infection (%)		Insect mortality ^b (%)	
Common name	Trade name	1 DAT	5 DAT	1 DAT	5 DAT
Carbofuran	Furadan 3 G	100 a	89 a	100 a	100 a
MIPC	MIPC 4 G	92 b	81 b	100 a	100 a
Bendiocarb	Garvox 5 G	85 b	59 c	100 a	100 a
BPMC	BPMC 4 G	84 b	61 c	100 a	100 a
Thiocyclam hydrogen oxalate	San 155 5 G	55 c	30 d	71 b	38 b
Disulfoton	Solvirex 5 G	34 cd	8 fg	100 a	100 a
Mephosfolan	Cytrolane 5 G	22 de	6 g	100 a	100 a
BHC	Hilbeeche 6 G	12 ef	10 f	24 c	10 c
Diazinon	Diazinon 6 G	8 ef	3 h	69 b	33 b
Quinalphos	Ekalux 5 G	5 fg	3 h	32 c	20 c
Lindane	Lindane 5 G	0 g	9 fg	26 c	17 c
Phorate-1	Phorate 10 G	0 g	0 i	100 a	100 a
Phorate-2	Thimet 10 G	0 g	14 e	100 a	100 a
Acephate	Orthene 75 WP	100 a	89 a	100 a	100 a
Carbofuran	Furadan 40 F	100 a	89 a	100 a	100 a
Bendiocarb	Ficam 80 WP	85 b	84 a	100 a	100 a
Carbaryl	Sevin 50 WP	85 b	84 a	100 a	100 a
MIPC	MIPC 50 WP	85 b	84 a	100 a	100 a
DDT	Hildit 50 WP	35 c	0 b	79 b	13 b
BHC	BHC 50 WP	20 d	0 b	40 c	2 c

^aDAT = days after treatment. Values followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at $P = 0.05$ by Duncan's multiple range test. ^bAdjusted values by Abbott's formula.

Greenhouse evaluation of emulsifiable concentrate insecticides against tungro virus infection

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Twenty-seven emulsifiable concentrate insecticides (see table) were tested in three trials in the nethouse to determine

their ability to prevent tungro virus infection.

Insecticides (0.1% concentration) were sprayed on 35-day-old Taichung Native 1 plants raised in 50 × 40 × 10 cm galvanized trays. Each insecticide treatment had 3 replications of 20 plants each. Each treated plant was inoculated with 2

viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* vectors at 1 and 5 days after treatment (DAT). An equal number of untreated plants were inoculated as control. Insect mortality was recorded 48 hours after caging, and infected plants were counted 20 days after inoculation. Prevention of virus infection was calculated:

$$\% \text{ prevention} = \frac{\% \text{ infected plants in control} - \% \text{ infected plants in treatment}}{\% \text{ infected plants in control}} \times 100$$